

Application and validation of SlideforMAP for assessing shallow landslide probability in New Zealand hill country

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Abstract

Shallow landslides are an important erosion process in New Zealand hill country. To mitigate this, silvopastoral landuse is often adopted. In such an environment, the correct placement of trees can improve slope stability. In this paper, we demonstrate the application of a shallow landslide model to identify optimal patterns of tree location. The model, SlideforMAP, is specifically designed to assess single tree location. We use an extended version of SlideforMAP with a dynamic computation of the soil saturation by macropore flow routing and a runoff rate coefficient for subsurface flow. The model is calibrated and validated for two New Zealand locations using observed data from a total of 578 shallow landslides identified in a 2010 inventory, partly related to an extreme precipitation event that occurred in March 2005. Single tree data containing tree location, height and species is included. The calibrated model parameters resulted in deep soils with low soil cohesion, low friction angle and high saturated conductivity. This indicates silt dominated soils, which is in agreement with available soil maps. Slight but inconsistent improvements in the accuracy are gained from the improved hydrological approach. Differences between the improvement and the original SlideforMAP are attributed to the non-steady-state approximation of sub-subsurface flow, rather than to the vegetation-influenced runoff rate coefficient. The optimized tree location pattern suggests that effective shallow landslide prevention in our study areas obtained by trees on slopes between 20° and 30° and under a lateral flux greater than 0.001 m²/s, i.e. mid-slope areas. SlideforMAP can help to visualize these areas more precisely and considering local soil conditions. This is a support tool for landowners and practitioners to optimally reduce erosion while maintaining productivity.

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1. Introduction

Shallow landslides are a direct hazard for humans and infrastructures. Additionally, they cause indirect effects on ecosystem services due to the loss of fertile soil and the mobilisation of sediments [1]. This is

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a concern in New Zealand, where past deforestation has caused a noticeable increase in shallow landslide activity that increased the volume of mobilised sediments at catchment scale and induced surface sheet and rill erosion [2]. A study in New Zealand hill country, an area with steep sloped pastoral farming, showed that approximately 15% of sediment is mobilised and recruited from rainfall-triggered shallow landslides [3]. This erosion causes unwanted effects ranging from land degradation to water quality reduction [2, 3]. An often applied measure to prevent shallow landsliding in New Zealand is the space-planting of trees, also known as silvopastoralism. This method enables erosion mitigation while maintaining pasture production [4]. Although this approach is applied in practice, research gaps remain concerning the effectiveness of silvopastoral systems [4, 5]. Shallow landslide probability can be modelled with different types of approaches and models, ranging from local to global models and with a probabilistic, deterministic or statistical approach [6]. Such models are essential for a holistic evaluation of landuses in the context of shallow landslide risk assessment [4] and for the prioritisation of bio-engineering measures at regional scale.

A key challenge for shallow landslide modelling is the quantification of hydrological processes and involved vegetation processes, which are fundamental to quantify the spatial distribution of shallow landslide probability at hillslope to catchment scale. On the local scale, root reinforcement dominates this spatial distribution [7, 8, 9, 10]. A number of challenges, related to data availability, scale and representation of vegetation management exist in modelling vegetation influence on shallow landsliding [11] and accordingly, stakeholders often resort to simple models.

The influence of trees on shallow landslide probability has been discussed in several studies [6, 12, e.g.]. These studies generally consider trees as slope stabilizing actors [13, 14, 15]. However, differences in root reinforcement between tree species, tree age and tree location are often poorly understood and insufficiently included in slope stability models [12, 14]. The inclusion of these local differences was shown to improve the reliability of slope stability models [16]. This improvement resulted from the inclusion of a spatio-temporal dynamic forest as compared to spatially uniform values of vegetation effect [17]. In addition, the work of van Zadelhoff et al. [13] concluded that applying a spatially heterogeneous root reinforcement model consistently improved shallow landslide probability prediction. They used a state-of-the-art probabilistic landslide model, SlideforMAP, which was specifically developed to consider in detail the effect of tree root reinforcement over large regions (1-100 km²), based on the detection of single trees.

One of the most challenging issues in the application of such event-based probabilistic models is the implementation of hydrological processes. Most of the coupled hydrological-shallow landslides models (e.g. TOPOG [18]) use a topographic-index approach [19] to model lateral subsurface flow. In this approach, the assumption is made that catchment-scale water storage is spatially "configured as if it was at steady state" [20]. Such topographic-index approaches can relate average catchment-scale moisture conditions to a spatial, topography-based pattern of likely saturated areas, without necessarily providing correct local moisture conditions [21, 22]. Apart from the often incorrect assumption that instantaneous catchment-scale moisture patterns are configured as for steady-state storage conditions, preferential flow, bedrock fractures, piping etc. [23] provide limitations. Shallow landslide susceptibility models using the topographic-index approach in their hydrological module generally mention the limitations of the approach, but argue that the benefits of the simplification (lower data and/or assumption requirements, faster computation enabling focus on larger areas) outweigh the shortcomings [24].

Besides the TOPOG approach, the rainfall-runoff modelling literature offers a few alternative methods to parsimoniously relate runoff generation to rainfall input and catchment physiographic conditions, i.e., to obtain estimates of runoff-available water without going through a full input-output streamflow model. One family of methods uses so-called runoff curves [25] to directly estimate the fraction of rainfall that becomes runoff from landuse and rainfall properties. The empirical SCS curve number (CN) is the most well known of these methods [26]: it relates runoff coefficients to landuse and soil type. A storage parameter provides temporal variability in the CN runoff coefficient. This method has however been developed for extreme events, namely for annual floods. We adopt here another runoff curve method, developed originally for Switzerland by Scherrer et al., [27] and Antonetti et al., [28]. These curves relate runoff coefficients to rainfall amounts and dominant runoff processes that are derived from land use and soil depth. There are only few other studies available that attempt a similar classification of dominant runoff processes (such as Hortonian overland flow or lateral subsurface flow) as a function of landscape characteristics, e.g. the work

of Savenije [29], which uses the Height Above Nearest Drainage, HAND, as classifier.

In this paper, we analyze the performance of different hydrological assumptions in SlideforMAP. We choose SlideforMAP due to its assumed compatibility for silvopastoral systems, where modelling the influence on the single trees is paramount. We compare three different versions of the model. Firstly, the original version, referred to as SfM original. Secondly, the new improved version that includes a runoff coefficient, referred here as SfM (without extension of the name). Additionally this version overcomes the topographic-index approach by enabling a dynamic lateral groundwater flux approach. Thirdly, we also test a hybrid version with dynamical lateral groundwater flux but no runoff coefficient, which is called SfM hybrid. This hybrid version is tested to isolate the influence of the runoff coefficient for comparison. The main aim of this research is to analyze the change in model performance of the improved version. We test the improvements by independent calibration and validation of generated shallow landslide probability maps. The selected study areas are two shallow landslide-prone study areas in New Zealand hill country, dominated by silvopastoral land use.

2. Methods

2.1. SlideforMAP

The shallow landslide probability model SlideforMAP [13] is based on the calculation of the Safety Factor (SF) for a high number (in the order of $10^5 - 10^7$, depending on study area size) of randomly located landslides (RLs, singular: RL) within a gridded study area domain and then assessing the landslide probability by taking the fraction of the amount of RLs with a $SF < 1$ to the total of the generated RLs overlapping a raster cell. Each RL has a random location and a surface area drawn from a calibrated inverse gamma distribution, with an assumed horizontally projected circular shape. For each RL, soil parameters are drawn from normal distributions and spatially variable parameters (slope angle, contributing area and root reinforcement) are obtained by averaging corresponding properties over the RL area. The SF for each RL is calculated based on a three dimensional force balance. The probabilistic approach has the advantage to explicitly incorporate the uncertainty in parameters values used for the SF calculations. Each single RL is indexed in the following equations with l , and the grids cells located within each RL are indexed with i .

2.2. General principle of the new hydrological module

The original version of SlideforMAP [13], uses a steady-state assumption of runoff given a constant precipitation input for the calculation of the pore water pressure. To investigate the effect of temporal rainfall input variation and of related moisture conditions, we implemented a new hydrological module. The new approach is based on runoff coefficients that depend on cumulative precipitation and furthermore assumes that lateral runoff has spatially uniform mean velocity depending only on rainfall intensity. No distinction is made between surface runoff and subsurface runoff. Figure 1 shows an overview of the improved hydrological module and further details are given in the corresponding sections below.

Fig. 1: Flowchart of the new hydrological module; the outcome is computed pore pressure, which as outcome that is used for the slope stability computation. *Optional. The computation of I_{rep} is only relevant in case of on-steady rainfall input.

2.3. From rainfall to lateral sub-surface flow

2.3.1. Computation of maximum runoff-contributing area

The spatial extent of the contributing area for each RL is computed by the D8 - flow raster algorithm [30] using Pysheds [31] on a raster resolution of 5 m. Within a RL of index l , the raster cell with the highest value of contributing area ($CA_{max,l}$) is selected for the computation of the maximum lateral runoff contributing to the build up of the pore water pressure. This raster cell is indexed i_{max} . The $CA_{max,l}$ is used as a mask to extract properties such as mean slope inclination and mean root reinforcement within the contributing area. Based on the D8 - flow raster, the distance of each raster cell within the contributing area j to i_{max} is computed. The concept of the $CA_{max,l}$ is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Schematic display of a RL with its hydrologically contributing area to its centre point in red and the maximum contributing area, $CA_{max,l}$, in orange. Grid resolution in the RL (2 m), with cells i and the contributing area (5 m), with cells j , is presented conceptually. The orange shaded area within the maximum contributing area of the RL highlights the effective contributing area, $CA_{eff,l}$, which is a function of precipitation intensity and duration (see Section 2.3.6)

2.3.2. Interception

Tree interception is subtracted from the cumulative rainfall for each rainfall event, for each raster cell. A grid cell is assumed covered by foliage when $RR_{max} > 0$. For raster cells with foliage cover, cumulative interception is computed using Equation 1 [32].

$$C = C_{max}(1 - \exp(-kP/C_{max})), \quad (1)$$

where C [mm] is the interception storage and C_{max} the maximum interception storage capacity. P [mm] is the total rainfall and k is a shape parameter [-], which moderates the degree of water detention. C_{max} and k are arbitrarily assumed to be 4 mm (well within the 2.2 to 8.3 mm range for C_{max} measured on tree basis by Herwitz., [33].) and 0.03 respectively. All intercepted water is assumed to re-evaporate immediately after the rainfall event and to be lost from the system.

2.3.3. Runoff coefficient

After correction for interception, we estimate for each rainfall event a runoff coefficient at the scale of the larger hydrological contributing area, $CA_{max,l}$ of the RL l . This runoff coefficient is the fraction of rainfall that results in lateral water mobilization during a rainfall event (surface runoff and lateral subsurface flow). The rest of the rainfall-event water is stored in the soil or percolates to deeper layers. Accordingly, the runoff coefficient is linked to the degree of saturation of the soil, which is important in the computation of slope stability.

The runoff coefficient depends on rainfall event structure (intensity, duration) and on soil properties. Here we use the method suggested by Antonetti et al., [28] to relate hillslope-scale runoff coefficients to cumulative rainfall of single rainfall events and to soil properties. The runoff coefficient is calculated for each raster cell RL l from the land use and rainfall properties in its $CA_{max,l}$. Their method uses rainfall-runoff curves (RRCs) that relate runoff coefficients to cumulative rainfall for five different runoff types that regroup one or several dominant hydrological runoff processes (Table 1). The method was developed based on sprinkler experiments and expert knowledge. It does not include antecedent soil moisture.

Table 1: Runoff types approach of Antonetti et al., [28]; HOF = Hortonian overland flow, SOF = Saturation-excess overland flow, SSF = sub-surface flow, DP = Deep percolation. Runoff Types are sub-classified by numbers.

Runoff Type	Dominant process	Response time	Soil depth
1	HOF1, HOF2, SOF1	Immediate	Very shallow soils/exposed bedrocks
2	SOF2, SSF1	Slightly delayed	Shallow soils
3	SSF2	Delayed	Moderately deep soils
4	SOF3, SSF3	Strongly delayed	Deep soil
5	DP	Not contributing	Very deep soils, wetlands

The RRCs used here [28] are based on previous research in Switzerland [34] (Figure 3). We approximate their shape by fitting the general function:

$$\psi(P) = a + b \cdot \log_{10}(P - S), P > 0; S < P, \quad (2)$$

where ψ is the runoff coefficient, P [mm] is the total precipitation, S [mm] is critical rainfall amount before runoff starts, a and b are shape and scale parameters. Both the cumulative and the derived instantaneous version (runoff rate coefficient) of the RRCs are described with Equation 2. For the computation of the maximum pore water pressure, the instantaneous version is used. The use of these RRCs requires the determination of the runoff types. For Switzerland, a decision scheme to assign a runoff type to an area was proposed by Scherrer et al., [27]. This decision scheme is based on soil type, slope angle, presence of macropores, soil depth, matrix permeability and soil water content before the rainfall event. This decision scheme and resulting classification has been developed for meadows and is not directly applicable to forested areas. However, it does consider the effects due to the presence of macropores and lateral preferential flow paths, which can be assumed to be influenced by the presence of tree roots. The presence of macropores can be assumed to increase the effective hydraulic conductivity in the subsurface and thus favour lateral flow, thereby reducing saturation-excess overland flow. An extensive adaptation of this decision scheme for forest types exists [35], but requires estimates for many input parameters. Based on previous research, we develop our own concise version for runoff type determination, including the effect due to roots. Firstly, a slope threshold is used to define areas with exposed bedrock, automatically classifying them as Runoff Type 1. We set this threshold to 50° . We assume all meadow and pasture areas have a slightly delayed runoff type (Runoff Type 2), which we call hereafter RT_{base} . Soil thickness is assumed to influence RT_{base} , as thicker soils can store more rainfall. The original method distinguishes deep and shallow soils and the limit between them is set to 1 m [27]), which we also adopt.

2.3.4. Accounting for macropores

The presence of vegetation in the contributing area is first of all taken into account via interception (Section 2.3.2), but additionally also via the effect of roots on preferential flows in macropores. We introduce the notation of RT_{min} , which is the runoff type yielding the lowest possible runoff amount for a given soil thickness. For shallow soil, RT_{min} is the delayed runoff (Runoff Type 3), for deep soils, RT_{min} is the strongly delayed flow (Runoff Type 4). We assume that the minimum runoff rate coefficient is affected by the presence of vegetation due to an increase in macropore flow. We model this effect of macropores by scaling the runoff rate coefficient as a function of lateral root reinforcement (as proxy variable), which is a parameter that is used in the calculation of the Safety Factor, SF (see Section 2.1).

For this runoff rate coefficient scaling, we define a fractional root reinforcement factor, called $F_{RR,l}$. $F_{RR,l}$ obtained as a fraction of the mean value of root reinforcement within the $CA_{max,l}$ and an assumed reference value of maximum lateral root reinforcement RR_{max} , which is set to 5 kN/m $F_{RR,l}$. The scaling of the runoff rate coefficient $\psi_{l,p}$ for a landslide RL and a cumulative precipitation P is then obtained as follows:

$$\psi_{l,p} = \psi_{RT_{min},p} + (\psi_{RT_{base},p} - \psi_{RT_{min},p}) \cdot F_{RR,l}, 0 < \psi_l < 1 \quad (3)$$

where $\psi_{RT_{base,P}}$ is the runoff rate coefficient corresponding to the base runoff type for landslide RL and cumulative precipitation P and $\psi_{RT_{min,P}}$ is the corresponding minimum runoff rate coefficient. An example of the results of the possible runoff rate coefficients, assuming various $F_{RR,l}$ values, calculated with Equation 3 are shown in Figure 3. We assume that any Hortonian overland runoff contributes to the RL-scale runoff generation, re-infiltrates or connect to the macropores network within the RL and contributes to lateral subsurface flow and thus to pore water pressure.

Fig. 3: Rainfall runoff curves according to the Runoff Types of Table 1. Top row shows the cumulative version of [28] (left) and the corresponding derived instantaneous version (right). Bottom row shows our cumulative curves for shallow soils (thickness < 1 m), left, and for deep soils (thickness > 1 m), right. For this the Scherrer et al., [27] soil thickness threshold was used. The blue curves in the bottom row show RRCs for 20 evenly distributed fractions of maximum root reinforcement.

The RRCs represent a simple tool to link rainfall and runoff. They have a solid theoretical basis as discussed in the work of Antonetti et al., [28]. Conceptually, the presence of macropores enhances the infiltration. In the first period of a rainfall event, this leads to a vertical preferential flow, which may saturate the lower horizons of the soil profile along a potential interface between the high permeability soil (with macropores) and a deeper low permeability horizons/bedrock. Once macropores are hydrologically connected, runoff is dominated by lateral surface or subsurface flow. These distinct phases of the runoff formation are the theoretical background for the RRCs in Figure 3.

2.3.5. Representative mean rainfall intensity

Applying the mean rainfall intensity from a rainfall event could lead to an underestimation of the maximum pore water pressure that in reality is more related to the peak intensity of a rainfall event. An example of such an underestimation is given in the Supplementary Material (Supp. material, Figure 2) where we applied a lateral flux example with an observed rainfall event using the hydrological module of SfM. To overcome this issue, we correct the mean precipitation intensity of an event by a correction factor (I_{corr}) to obtain a representative peak rainfall intensity (I_{rep}). This correction factor is the difference between the maximum soil water flux based on a dynamic precipitation intensity and the one based on a constant mean precipitation intensity. I_{corr} is assumed to be dependent on the following factors: contributing area

extent, contributing area elongation, macropore flow velocity, precipitation event duration and precipitation intensity variability in time.

We compute I_{corr} for a random 5% subset (for computational reasons) of the contributing areas in both of our study areas, with the inclusion of our runoff rate coefficient methodology. The results are plotted versus the contributing area size, which we expect to be the best and most practical predictor of this ratio (see Results Section, Figure 8). The resulting relationship of I_{corr} to $CA_{max,i}$ is then used to connect I_{corr} and $CA_{max,i}$ for all contributing areas. This method is applied to all model versions.

2.3.6. Effective contributing area

To compute the effective contributing area $CA_{eff,i}$ from the maximum contributing area $CA_{max,i}$, an estimation of lateral flow velocity is essential. We assume that this lateral flow velocity is dominated by the contribution of preferential macropore flow. Typical macropore flow velocity varies between 10^{-1} and 10^{-5} [36], with a geometric mean of $1.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m/s. This can be 2-3 orders of magnitude higher than soil matrix mean flow velocity. Findings similar to this are reported in the work of Beven et al., [37].

Gao et al., [36] reviewed and analyzed the relationship between precipitation intensity and macropore flow velocity in 76 global studies over different soils and land cover. We use the resulting linear relationship for all data points to define macropore velocity (V_{mac}) as a function of macropore diameter and rainfall intensity [36, Equation 2]. It is assumed that the effective contributing area $CA_{eff,i}$ [m^2] is a function of time (t), of lateral flow velocity and of total contributing area ($CA_{max,i}$). We define the contributing fraction of the total contributing area by the fraction of cells that satisfy the condition: $L_c < tV_{mac}$, where L_c is the distance of a contributing area cell, c , to its outlet (cell within RL l with $CA_{max,i}$). The effective contributing area $CA_{eff,i}$ is then obtained by multiplying the contributing fraction with $CA_{max,i}$. The lateral flux, $Q_{max,i}$ [m^3/s], is calculated as a function of time, using Equation 4 [38]:

$$Q_{max,i}(t) = I_{rep} \cdot CA_{eff,i}(t) \cdot \psi(P). \quad (4)$$

In this equation, ψ [-] is the runoff rate coefficient, which is a function of the cumulative precipitation P . I_{rep} [m/s] is the representative precipitation intensity, obtained by multiplying the mean intensity I [m/s] with a multiplication factor I_{corr} [-]. This enables us to estimate the degree of saturation of each cell, i , in the RL as a function of time at the outlet using a modified TOPOG approach as below:

$$h_{sat,i}^*(t) = \frac{Q_{max,i}(t) \cdot \left(\frac{CA_i}{CA_{max,i}} \right)}{K_{sat} \cdot H_{soil} \cdot \sin(s_i) \cdot b}. \quad (5)$$

In this equation, CA_i is the specific contributing area for an individual cell i in the RL. K_{sat} [m/s] is the saturated hydraulic conductivity parallel to slope, averaged over the soil depth. H_{soil} [m] is the soil thickness. s_i is the slope angle in degrees per cell i . b [m] is the raster cell resolution. Averaging $h_{sat,i}^*$ [-] over all cells gives the RL h_{sat}^* . Subsequent pore water pressure is computed as:

$$P_{water} = H_{soil} \cdot \cos(s) \cdot h_{sat}^* \cdot g \cdot \rho_w, \quad (6)$$

where P_{water} [Pa] is the pore water pressure, s is the average slope angle of the RL, g [9.81 m/s^2] is the gravitational acceleration, ρ_{water} [998 kg/m^3] is the density of water.

2.4. Passive earth pressure

Passive earth pressure acting as resistance force at the bottom of the RL is included applying the results of Cislighi et al. [39], in accord with the framework proposed by Schwarz et al. [40]. Root compressing forces in this calculation are included and estimated to be 10% of the lateral root reinforcement under tension [40, 9]. The contribution of passive earth pressure forces to RL stability are implemented by adding them to the other stabilizing forces (shearing forces and maximum tensile lateral root forces).

2.5. Model calibration and validation

The improved model has a total of 20 parameters. Three of these are probabilistic. An overview of the parameters is given in Table 2. We only retain four sensitive parameters [13] for calibration and assign default values, estimates or literature values, to the remaining parameters (Table 2).

Table 2: An overview of all SfM parameters. Table is adapted from van Zadelhoff et al., [13]. The only difference is the substitution of the transmissivity by the saturated hydraulic conductivity K_{sat} . Transmissivity is the product of the K_{sat} and the soil thickness. The last column in the table indicates whether the parameter is to be calibrated.

Parameter	Description	Default value	Unit	Calibration
m_d	Soil thickness mean	1	m	Yes
σ_d	Soil thickness standard deviation	0.25	m	No
m_C	Soil cohesion mean	2	kPa	Yes
σ_C	Soil cohesion standard deviation	0.5	kPa	No
m_ϕ	Angle of internal friction mean	30	°	Yes
σ_ϕ	Angle of internal friction standard deviation	4	°	No
ρ_{ls}	Density of the random generated landslides	0.2	RLs/m ²	No
ρ_{soil}	Dry soil density	1500	kg/m ³	No
K_{sat}	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	0.1	m/s	Yes
I	The precipitation event that is tested	10	mm/hr	No
I_{min}	Precipitation intensity threshold for instability	1.2	mm/hr	No
r_{xy}	Raster resolution	2	m	No
l_{wr}	Ratio between length and width of the landslides	2	-	No
C_{max}	Maximum interception storage capacity	4	mm	No
k	Interception curve shape parameter	0.03	-	No
c	Fitting parameter for the lateral root reinforcement	25068.54	-	No
α_1	Shape of root distribution in horizontal direction	0.862	-	No
β_1	Rate of root distribution in horizontal direction	3.225	-	No
α_2	Shape of root distribution in vertical direction	1.284	-	No
β_2	Rate of root distribution in vertical direction	3.688	m	No
$D_{\text{trees,max}}$	maximum distance for influence of tree roots	15	m	No
ρ_{tree}	Density of a tree	850	kg/m ³	No
ρ_{water}	Density of water	998	kg/m ³	No

The calibration parameters and their corresponding ranges are given in Table 3. Contrary to our previous work, we do not include precipitation intensity because detailed rainfall data from radar imagery is available. Accordingly, saturated hydraulic conductivity (transmissivity in van Zadelhoff et al., [13]) and mean soil thickness are the only calibration parameters in the computation of pore water pressure. Furthermore, parameters related to the vegetation are also not included in the calibrated parameter set; we use here single tree detected trees (Section 3) and assign the parameters related to root reinforcement ($c, \alpha_1, \beta_1, \alpha_2, \beta_2$) directly based on the identified tree species (see Section 3). This has proven to be the best performing method of including vegetation effects in SlideforMAP [13]. For calibration and validation, we use a split sample test, splitting the available observations into spatial subsets. We divide the study area into 10,000 small subsets i.e. terrain units and subsequently classify the terrain units for either validation or calibration. Throughout the calibration and validation process, the classification is immutable.

Table 3: Parameters for the calibration with initial value ranges.

Calibration parameter	Unit	Description	Initial value range
m_d	m	Mean soil thickness	0.20 - 1.80
m_C	kPa	Mean saturated soil cohesion	0.00 - 12.5
m_ϕ	°	Mean angle of internal friction	24.00 - 41.50
K_{sat}	m/s	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	10^{-8} - 10^{-2}

For the split sampling, we arrange the terrain units by slope angle and then take a random 85% / 15% sample in a method similar to the performance evaluation in the work of Frattini et al. [41], where it is suggested that a terrain unit based on slope angle, comprised of multiple grid cells, is a better terrain unit than single grid cells. The 85% / 15% ratio is a recommendation by Guzetti et al., [42].

We calibrate the model based on an iterative parameter sampling technique, which will not necessarily yield the best possible parameter set (which in any case would be spuriously influenced by observational uncertainties), but has the advantage of yielding additional insights into the parameter ranges that perform well [13]. The method uses a total of three parameter sampling cycles. For the first cycle, we sample 150 unique calibration parameter sets from the prior parameter ranges of Table 3 with Latin Hypercube Sampling [43]. Each of these parameter sets is used to run the model twice (to account for the inherent probabilistic variation) and the corresponding model performance is evaluated with the Area Under the Curve (AUC) from the Receiver Operator Curve method [44]. The AUC value is computed for each model run for all terrain units that were retained for calibration. For a given sampled parameter set, the mean AUC of the two runs is taken as performance evaluator. Subsequently, the 150 values sampled per calibration parameter are ordered and grouped into 0.1 percentile fractions, for which the mean AUC is computed.

The 5 fractions with the highest mean AUC value (i.e. 50% of the total fractions) are retained as prior range for the next sampling cycle. After the third sampling cycle, the single parameter set with the highest AUC values is retained as calibration parameter set and used in the subsequent validation. With the new model formulation for groundwater table and pore water pressure computation, a challenge is the fraction of RLs that are fully saturated, which can become unreasonably high. We remove calibration parameter sets that lead to saturated fractions higher than 0.5, which is a heuristic choice.

3. Data

For the application of SfM, we use two study areas in New Zealand that are dominated by silvopastoral farming. Location and overview of the areas is given in Figure 4. Digital terrain models (DTM) for the study areas were provided by Spiekermann et al., [5]. The DTM is resampled using bi-linear resampling to a resolution of 2 m. This corresponds to a resolution proven to give good results in SlideforMAP [13].

Fig. 4: Location of the study areas in the Wellington region on New Zealand's North Island. Upper right is Te Whanga (short: TW), lower right is Waikoukou (short: WA). In green are given single tree locations, in red shallow landslides from the inventory. All coordinates are in WGS84.

A manually corrected automated landslide scar identification algorithm produced a dataset of 43069 shallow landslides [45], which overlaps our study areas. We use 500 scars for Te Whanga and 78 for Waikoukou. 14 shallow landslides were excluded based on fieldwork that identified them as cattle trampling rather than shallow landslides. The aerial imagery is from 2010 and the identified shallow landslides are considered largely to be related to events in March 2005 and July 2006 [45]. An overview is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Study area characteristics. * Indicates the study area as used in Spiekermann et al. [45]. The size reduction of the study areas in this paper is for computational efficiency purposes.

Name	Surface area km ²	Inventory n landslides
Te Whanga	3.5	500
Te Whanga farm*	17.2	3271
Waikoukou	1.4	78
Waikoukou farm*	4.6	755

Gridded hourly precipitation totals are available through the MOANA dataset [46]. This interpolated grid is based on radar data. To confirm internal consistency of the precipitation data in our study areas, double mass curves for all radar grid cells that overlap our study areas are given in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Double mass plot validation of precipitation data consistency. Shown is the cumulative precipitation of one raster cell over the entire radar data period (x-axis) plotted against mean cumulative precipitation of all raster cells (y-axis). Red: raster cells in the Waikoukou study area. Blue; raster cells in the Te Whanga study area.

This data is used to identify probable events that initiated shallow landslides and to give an idea of the corresponding precipitation intensity and return period. A plot of most extreme events and the computation of return periods in the study areas prior to the landslide inventory is shown in the Supp. Material (Figure 1). For model validation in both study areas, we focus on the March 2005 event. We retain this event because it has the highest return period for the radar observational period but we know that not all landslides were triggered by this single event. Details of the event are presented in Table 5 and in Figure 6. The event had a high variability of precipitation intensity and was more extreme (in terms of amounts) in Waikoukou than in Te Whanga, indicating significant spatial precipitation variation.

Table 5: The most extreme event from the two study areas over the period of 2000 - 2010. I is the precipitation intensity (mm/hr) and T is the return period (years).

	Te Whanga	Waikoukou
Event start	29-3-2005 05:00	29-3-2005 05:00
Duration	33 hours	33 hours
I	4.3 mm/hr	7.1 mm/hr
T	10 years	173 years

Fig. 6: Hourly precipitation graph of the March 29-30 2005 precipitation event in the two study areas.

Trees in the study area have been mapped using available LiDAR data from 2013/14 in the Wellington region of New Zealand [5], which was processed with the PyCrown model [47] to delineate tree crowns. The center point X and Y of the tree crown is assumed to be the tree location. Properties of the inventoried shallow landslides as compared to the properties of the total study area are given in Table 6. We assume that no changes have taken places on trees between 2005 (time of the larger landslides events) and the LiDAR data collection.

Table 6: Properties of the inventoried shallow landslide scars as compared to the properties of the total study area. The average distance to the nearest tree, obtained as average over all raster cells, is computed after removing all distances > 15 m, beyond trees are assumed to exert no effect.

	Waikoukou		Te Whanga	
	Total study area	Shallow landslide scars	Total study area	Shallow landslide scars
Total surface area [ha]	142.6	0.6	351.7	3.4
Mean elevation [m.a.s.l.]	218.0	210.5	197.6	189.0
Mean slope angle [°]	19.9	26.4	21.5	28.6
Mean contributing area [m ²]	8432.3	100.3	4158.9	13089.1
Mean distance to nearest tree [m]	11.7	14.0	12.9	12.9

Species classification was conducted with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) and based on orthophotos (2010 - 2017) and the tree crown [5]. The resulting data includes the X and Y coordinate of the tree, the tree crown height and the classified species (eucalyptus, kanuka, poplar/willow, pine, undefined). Characteristics of the vegetation based on this data and of soil data in the two study areas is given in Table. 7.

Table 7: Study area characteristics. Soil depth and soil texture class are taken from S-map soil mapping for New Zealand [48].

	Waikoukou	Te Whanga
Number of trees	2304	3747
Dominant tree species	Kanuka (52%)	Kanuka (50%)
Sub-dominant tree species	Poplar/Willow (32%)	Poplar/Willow (45%)
Tree density [Trees/ha]	16	11
Average tree height [m]	16.8	11.5
Dominant soil depth class	Shallow (41%)	Moderate deep (83%)
Sub-dominant soil depth class	Deep (30%)	Deep (16%)
Dominant soil texture class	Silt (100%)	Silt (91%)
Sub-dominant soil texture class	-	Loam (8%)

Parameterization of the maximum lateral root reinforcement as a function of tree distance is available for poplar [49] and pine (*Pinus Radiata*) [50]. In the work of Spiekermann et al., [5], a normalized tree influence with distance from the stem is given, based on a statistical analysis in the same study areas. We use their equations (shown in Figure 7) to extend our reclassification of the tree species for which we have no root reinforcement parametrization.

Fig. 7: Normalized tree root influence as a function of distance from the stem. Parameterization based on Spiekermann et al. [5, Figure 10].

Due to the incompatibility of the statistical method, which implicitly includes all vegetation effects, with our probabilistic physical method, we cannot relate the tree influence equations directly to root reinforcement, but have to use it as an indication. We choose to apply poplar root reinforcement parameterization

for kanuka, eucalyptus and undefined trees. This is because, within the most effective distance (up to approximately 7 m), poplars exert a comparable vegetation influence (Figure 7) to the other tree species. A comparison between pine and kanuka trees shows that a standard kanuka stand provides a higher reinforcement for the first 8 years of growth, but lower reinforcement thereafter [51]. Root tensile strength of kanuka, before felling, is almost two times higher than that of pine (32.45 vs. 17.62 MPa) [52].

4. Results

We first present the analysis of the multiplication factors I_{CORR} to obtain the representative rainfall intensity I_{rep} based on observed mean precipitation intensity per event, I . Figure 8 shows the simulation results for a single precipitation event, the one of March 2005 as a function of catchment area, for the full model. Corresponding results for a fixed runoff rate coefficient and no runoff rate coefficient scenario are given in the Supp. material (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Fig. 8: Ratio between the maximum lateral flow rate computed with an actual precipitation event and with a constant mean precipitation with a runoff rate coefficient dependent on lateral root reinforcement for the March 2005 event (with 33 h duration). Each point in the plot represents one RL. Soil thickness classification between deep and shallow soils is derived from random sampling. The shown regression lines are: The Waikoukou, intercept 5.7 and slope -0.98; The Te Whanga, intercept 6.3 and slope -1.08. To add context, for some outliers the contributing area outlines are given, with their outlet in black.

The identified relation between the flow ratios and contributing areas of Figure 8 matches our expectations, with large areas having a lower ratios. These ratios can be directly related to I_{corr} because of the assumed linear relationship between throughfall and interception (equation 4). In small catchments, the infiltrated rainfall travels a small distance to the outlet and has a more instantaneous reaction. This means that the peak lateral flux is more directly related to the peak rainfall intensity, resulting in a large I_{CORR} . For larger contributing areas, the flux at the outlet is a mixture of different precipitation intensities occurring at different locations in the contributing area at different moments in time, meaning the lateral flux corresponds better to the mean precipitation intensity of the event. This behaviour is visible for certain elongated contributing areas in Figure 8 for Te Whanga and for the example contributing area in Figure 2 with the inclusion of the runoff rate coefficient. Due to the dependency of the flow ratio on many factors and on the precipitation event, we are forced to make a generalization. We therefore use the identified relations between the flow ratio and the contributing area size in Figure 8.

4.1. Calibration and validation

The iterative parameter sampling leads to a consistent narrowing of the parameter ranges for the three model versions tested here (Table 8, corresponding dot-plot are given in the Supp. Material, Section

3). The calibration procedure is run at a shallow landslide density (ρ_{1s}) of 0.20 RLs/m². After calibrated parameter values are determined, these are input for a final split-sample run. This run and all subsequent results are computed with $\rho_{1s} = 0.75$ RLs/m² to make full use of computational efficiency.

Table 8: Overview of the calibration and validation results for the model versions of this study. Per study area, the first subgroup gives the calibrated parameter values and the narrowed parameter range from the last calibration cycle. The second subgroup gives metrics of performance. These are the AUC, The unstable fraction (UF), which is the fraction of random landslides that has a safety factor < 1.0 and the Saturated Fraction (SAF) which the fraction of Random landslides that has a relative saturation ($h_{sat,i}^*$) of 1.0 for the part (85% of the study area) of the study area used in the calibration. The last subgroup gives the same metrics for the part (15% of the study area) used for validation. Between brackets for SfM original and SfM hybrid (no Ψ) are the metrics when they are ran with the calibrated parameters from SfM.

	SfM		SfM original		SfM hybrid	
Waikoukou						
m_d [m]	1.32	(0.64-1.52)	0.98	(0.64-1.42)	1.41	(0.52-1.52)
m_C [kPa]	2.06	(0.06-2.04)	2.15	(0.09-2.05)	0.32	(0.06-2.03)
m_ϕ [°]	25.5	(24.0-29.6)	26.6	(24.1, 28.4)	25.7	(24.0-27.5)
K_{sat} [m/s]	0.0075	(0.0004-0.0075)	0.0006	(0.0005-0.0065)	0.0080	(0.0004-0.0081)
Calibration AUC	0.899		0.864	(0.910)	0.902	(0.899)
Calibration UF	0.124		0.357	(0.112)	0.251	(0.125)
Calibration SAF	0.0159		0.3446	(0.0152)	0.0143	(0.0162)
Validation AUC	0.863		0.814	(0.879)	0.878	(0.864)
Validation UF	0.128		0.357	(0.116)	0.255	(0.129)
Validation SAF	0.0172		0.3433	(0.0168)	0.0155	(0.0179)
Te Whanga						
m_d [m]	1.29	(1.09, 1.48)	1.44	(1.06-1.53)	1.48	(1.25-1.56)
m_C [kPa]	0.33	(0.03, 2.51)	1.56	(0.05-2.03)	0.64	(0.14-2.10)
m_ϕ [°]	27.4	(24.1-28.2)	28.2	(24.1-29.3)	28.0	(24.1-29.2))
K_{sat} [m/s]	0.0068	(0.0021-0.0074)	0.0056	(0.0004-0.0057)	0.0060	(0.0002-0.0063)
Calibration AUC	0.866		0.854	(0.848)	0.867	(0.865)
Calibration UF	0.232		0.129	(0.211)	0.201	(0.229)
Calibration SAF	0.0128		0.0153	(0.0126)	0.0131	(0.0117)
Validation AUC	0.896		0.888	(0.887)	0.896	(0.897)
Validation UF	0.224		0.125	(0.205)	0.194	(0.222)
Validation SAF	0.0169		0.0201	(0.0173)	0.0176	(0.0159)

Calibrated parameter values are largely consistent for the two case studies and the tested model versions, especially when compared to the initial parameter ranges. It is however important to note that the calibration parameter ranges and the values for different versions can only be compared qualitatively, since the exact value is dependent on model process uncertainties. Most notable is the low mean soil cohesion for SfM and SfM hybrid in both study areas and the low K_{sat} for SfM original for Waikoukou. This low K_{sat} , directly results in a high Saturated Area Fraction, SAF, of RLs. Calibration and validation metrics (AUC, SAF and UF) for the three compared model versions are largely consistent for the two case studies. Minor differences between the calibration and the validation metrics, is to be expected due to observational and modelling uncertainties [53, 54]. The random split sampling of the modelling domain into 85% for calibration and 15% for validation probably also plays a certain role.

Overall, we see that SfM performs marginally better than SfM original for both case studies, despite of their considerable difference in size (142.6 h versus 351.7 ha). The performance of SfM hybrid is closer to the one of the new version than to the one of SfM original for both study areas. One notable exception occurs

in SfM original in the Waikoukou study area, here the calibrated performance is worse than the performance using a different calibration set (SfM parameters). This can only indicate an inadequacy in our calibration procedure. A further indication for this is the deviancy in the calibrated K_{sat} and elevated degree of (34% of total RLs) complete soil saturation.

4.2. Hydrological module

The average pore water pressure resulting from the calibrated parameter values of Table 8 for SfM is shown in Figure 9 for Te Whanga. Corresponding results for Waikoukou are available in the Supp. Material Figure 10. The average pressure and difference to SfM original under SfM calibration, SfM original with unique calibration and the hybrid version are also listed. The spatial patterns of pore water pressure resulting from the retained parameter sets for each model, show small differences on the hillslope tops but strong differences close to the stream network. This difference reflects the distribution of contributing area and to a minor extend the location of single trees. Significant influence of the calibration can be seen as well related to values of K_{sat} and m_d , which do not so much influence the pattern, but the overall 'background' value of pore pressure.

Fig. 9: Calibrated pore water pressure in Te Whanga. Upper row, mean pore water pressure [kPa] from SfM, SfM original with SfM parametrization, SfM original, with unique calibration and SfM no hybrid; Lower row list the absolute difference in pore water pressure of the versions as compared to SfM.

4.3. Landslide probability

A key check that the model behaves well is the assessment of computed shallow landslide susceptibility on areas that have experienced landslides according to the inventory. Here we focus on SfM as it is the main result we want to present in this paper. SfM computed landslide probability maps resulting from the calibration parameters (Table 8) for the two study areas are given in Figure 10 and 11. The lower probability values in Waikoukou are noticeable. This correlates to the unstable fraction of surface area in Table 6, where it is shown that Te Whanga has a higher relative and absolute unstable area. This is also reflected in the calibration and validation results (Table 8), with Te Whanga having a higher unstable fraction resulting in the calibrated runs.

Fig. 10: SfM Landslide probability results in Waikoukou

Fig. 11: SfM Landslide probability results in Te Whanga

The computed distribution of susceptibility clearly shows that in both study areas SfM is generally capable of reproducing the shallow landslides from the inventory. This pattern appears to be dominated by slope angle. The similarity in validation AUC values, despite a significantly lower UF indicates that the pattern in landslide probability is important and the absolute probability values are arbitrary. Performance can be better visualized by making a cumulative graph of the probability values for both study areas and the inventoried landslide scars. This is displayed in Figure 12.

Fig. 12: Left: Empirical cumulative distribution functions of the shallow landslide probability for the entire study area (orange) and the surface area from the landslides in the inventory (blue). In addition, the boxplot of the distribution of probability values for the landslide scars is shown. Figure Left: Waikoukou, Figure right: Te Whanga.

Here we see the same pattern as seen in Table 8 and in Figure 11 and 10, with Te Whanga having overall higher landslide probability values. Both study areas appear to have a well distinguishable curves for inventory probability values and overall probability values. In addition, we check if the hydrological model indicators are distributed similarly on the landslide area as compared to the total area. We present these as boxplots in Figure 13. We see a stronger discrepancy in all indicators for Waikoukou. For both study areas, the median and mean contribution coefficient ($CA_{eff,i}/CA_{max,i}$) and median runoff rate coefficient is higher for the landslide scars. Lateral root reinforcement is lower for the shallow landslide scars. There seems to be no significant difference in distribution in the shallow landslide size for all unstable RLs and the shallow landslide scars.

Fig. 13: Boxplots of some key model indicators, of the entire study area (orange) and cells in the landslide inventory (blue). Key indicators are the contribution coefficient ($CA_{eff,i}/CA_{max,i}$), runoff rate coefficient (Ψ) and the lateral root reinforcement. Additionally, we added a boxplot of observed landslide size (size of landslides in the inventory in blue and the distribution of size of RLs that have a stability factor, $Sf < 1$ in orange; Figure Left: Waikoukou, Figure right: Te Whanga.

We also check the relationship of lateral flux with slope angle for the SfM results and the inventoried landslides in accordance with the methodology of Prancevic et al., [55] in Figure 14. All RLs with a computed $Sf < 1.0$ are plotted. Setting aside spatial variation in root reinforcement and soil parameters, these are the only indicators influencing the shallow landslide susceptibility pattern.

Fig. 14: Computed lateral flux for the inventoried shallow landslide scars and the unstable random landslides from the calibrated SfM (random sample of 10% for better visibility), plotted versus the slope angle. Linear regressions (none significant) for the points are given.

It can be seen that the RLs mapped as unstable match the properties of the majority of the inventoried landslides, with a sweet spot on a slope angle between 20 to 30 ° and a specific discharge of 0.001 to 0.01 m²/s. For both study areas, it appears the model classifies a wide range of slope angles and contributing areas (Figure 14) as unstable, decreasing the accuracy. The model tends to overestimate slope instabilities in steep slopes (> 35 °). Especially since the inventory in Figure 14 displays quite a narrow slope range. The trendlines of the shallow landslide scars and the RLs do not match up well. It appears the inventory trendlines are influenced heavily by outliers with high lateral flux or from another perspective: the model overestimates instability in shallow landslides with a low computed lateral flux. We also see a subset of inventoried shallow landslides displaying a very high lateral flux, indicating they overlap with the bottom of hollows. SfM appears capable of classifying these areas as unstable.

5. Discussion

5.1. Limitations

The objective of the model improvements presented here was to improve the representation of the conditions of shallow landslides initiation, i) in hydrological terms, by pore water pressure and vegetation characteristics by root reinforcement and ii) in mechanical terms by means of passive earth pressure. However, uncertainties arise from model shortcomings, local inhomogeneities or from parts of the inventory not being related to our modelled event.

The large variation and magnitude in unstable fraction (UF, Table 8) through the study areas and model versions is remarkable. It is an order of magnitude higher than the actual fraction of the study areas that suffered shallow landsliding (Table 6). We believe the variation is partly related to variation in the calibrated mean soil cohesion. The overall large values of UF can be due to the use of AUC as performance measure. The AUC may not be the best measure in validating physical models as it is a relative measure where the absolute probability values are ambiguous. For practitioners, we recommend relating shallow landslide probability values to said values in known landslide scars, akin to what is shown in Figure 12 as presented in this manuscript. Practitioners can decide how much of instability they want to capture and how much uncertainty they take into account by taking a certain fraction of actual landslide scars and extrapolating this to a threshold on the probability values.

5.2. SlideforMAP improvements

A key challenge in the use of observed precipitation events is how to account for effects related to precipitation falling on different parts of the contributing area and to subsequent different (unknown) surface or subsurface flow paths, which lead to a temporal dispersion of flow contributions at a point of interest (which is commonly addressed in rainfall-runoff modelling literature, [56, 57, e.g.]). This makes it challenging to relate properties of the precipitation event to the maximum lateral flux, which in turn relates to the highest pore water pressure. We tackle this here by converting precipitation to subsurface lateral flow by i) a runoff rate coefficient and ii) by correcting the reference precipitation for the size of the contributing area. Both improvements are, to the best of our knowledge, novel for comparable landslide models.

However, the difference in performance of between the model versions is negligible (Table 8). For Waikoukou, SfM original even performs better. For Te Whanga, where the majority of the inventoried landslides lie (500 vs 78), SfM (and SfM hybrid) perform slightly better than SfM original. The change in pore water pressure due to the hydrological improvements is visible 9. Comparing the pore water pressure of SfM to SfM original under similar calibration shows a higher modelled pressure on the ridges for SfM than for SfM original and a lower modelled pore water pressure in the valleys. The lower value in the valleys corresponds to a smaller $CA_{eff,l}$ and the higher value on the ridges likely stems from the use of $CA_{max,l}$ for scaling (rather than taking the mean contributing area of a RL as in SfM original, Equation 4 and 5).

Influence of the vegetation on the pore water pressure appears minor, as visible from the low difference in performance metrics between SfM and SfM hybrid. A multitude of reasons, or a combinations thereof, can be invoked: i) None of our improvements significantly distinguished unstable areas from stable areas and therefore the AUC measured performance does not improve. ii) The use of an area-relationship to find a representative rainfall intensity I_{rep} , as applied in both the original and in the new version is very effective and overrules performance gains related to any other improvement. A hint of this might be that near identical performance of SfM hybrid shows that at least the runoff rate coefficient is of little effect. iii) Our improvements in SfM do not capture the unique conditions of outliers in the inventory, especially in terms of contributing area. This is best seen in Figure 14. iiiii) The AUC performance measure is not a good metric for capturing marginal gains in accuracy and therefore cannot highlight performance improvements.

Accordingly, from a landslide susceptibility perspective, we cannot definitively say if SfM or SfM original should be preferred for practical applications. We do however believe that our new hydrological module is closer to reality since stationary lateral flow conditions (as assumed in SfM original) are very rare in nature [19]. Future work, and in particular additional case studies, will certainly yield additional evidence.

5.3. Vegetation

In SfM original, vegetation acts in a mechanical sense, by lateral/basal root reinforcement and vegetation weight. In SfM version, two additional hydrological effects are included, namely: reduction in the runoff rate coefficient near vegetation and a reduction in precipitation amount by interception. However, lateral root reinforcement can be assumed to be the vegetation parameter with the highest impact on slope stability computation in SfM: it was shown to be the most sensitive parameter in original SfM original [13]. In the Waikoukou study area, the difference in mean distance to trees between the whole study area and the inventoried landslides (Table 4) suggests a general propensity of shallow landsliding further away from the trees. This is also shown in Figure 13, where root reinforcement correlates with more stable areas. This effect is strongest in Waikoukou and less strong in Te Whanga. Regardless of the model version, of the calibrated parameter combinations or of the study area used, our validation AUC is above 0.8, indicating good predictive performance [58]. We have assumed our trees to be either poplar or pine trees. This meant a reclassification of a large number of kanuka trees to poplar trees. Using statistical relationships on the relative effects of both tree species [5], we argue the effects of this differences is small.

One main vegetation-dependent effects is not included in SfM: the effect of evapotranspiration (beyond evaporation of intercepted water) and the effect of heterogeneous infiltration in vegetated soils. Evapotranspiration can be assumed to be of minor importance during extreme precipitation events relevant for landslide triggering [59]. However, evapotranspiration over longer time periods, possible coupled with an increased macropore presence, could reduce antecedent moisture in vegetated areas. This effect is partially

addressed here with the estimated runoff rate coefficients. However, the calibration and validation results show that the way we implemented this effect did not lead to significantly different results, indicating either the antecedent moisture itself was not significant for this specific event or our implementation with the runoff curves was ineffective.

5.4. Research outlook

The availability of hourly rainfall data by the MOANA project helped in this research. This data avoids using precipitation intensity as a calibration parameter or making broad assumptions. This contributed to a more realistic validity test of our improvements with less uncertainty compensated by the calibrated parameters. We think this type of data creates opportunities for new concepts in rain-induced shallow landslide modelling as illustrated here. As discussed earlier in this paper, this is not the first attempt to overcome the stationary-flow assumption in landslide probability modelling. The presented method to overcome the stationarity assumption requires only a low number of parameters but was shown here to lead to only small improvements in terms of model performance. This might potentially be due to the fact that rainfall uncertainty largely dominates total modelling uncertainty, which is a well-known fact in hydrological modelling [60, 61, e.g.]. Passive earth pressure is often neglected in shallow landslide models [6]. Here we implemented this pressure as its maximum mobilized amount. Cohen et al., [9] numerically estimates that only a portion of this pressure is mobilized at any given moment of shallow landslide displacement. Definitive research and implementation of this portion could improve current models.

Finally, we would like to emphasize that plotting contributing area vs. slope angle from the inventoried shallow landslides (Figure 14) displays outlier landslides in terms of the combinations of lateral flux and slope angle, which still remains a mystery as these outliers are distant from the SfM sweet spot of slope angles between 20 - 30 ° and a lateral flux between 0.001 to 0.01 m²/s. One reason for these outliers might be the absence of antecedent moisture assumptions in the model, which could be improved in the future. In combination with more reliable spatial rainfall data, this might show more clearly if dynamic hydrology can perform better than the stationarity assumption under a variety of conditions.

6. Conclusion

In this study we calibrated, validated and compared the performance of the original version of SlideforMAP, an improved version and a hybrid version in two shallow landslide-prone study areas in New Zealand hill country. The improved model version includes the following new features: it computes an event-based effective contributing area per random landslide, a runoff rate coefficient based on root reinforcement in the contributing area and it includes passive earth pressure forces in the stability calculations. The calibrated and validated model parameters displays a tendency to deep soils, low soil cohesion a low friction angle and high saturated hydraulic conductivity, influenced by macropore flow. The improved version of SlideforMAP performs marginally better than the original model version in Te Whanga study area; in the Waikoukou study area performance is slightly worse, with a calibration imprecision in the results. The hybrid version, without runoff rate coefficient, performs near similar to the new version. This suggests that the inclusion of non-stationary flow, by means of an effective contributing catchment ($CA_{eff,l}$), is the main model improvement. The runoff rate coefficient is either of little influence or to be inefficiently incorporated in our model.

In terms of case-study specific results, the obtained landslide probability maps for the two case studies show that shallow landslide occurrence in our study areas is concentrated on slopes between 20° and 30° and under a lateral flux higher than 0.001 m²/s. This mostly corresponds to mid-slope regions, where enough contributing area is present and which could greatly benefit from space-planted trees. Overall, SlideforMAP has been shown to perform satisfactorily for the two case studies in New Zealand. Compared to the original three case studies in Switzerland [13], the new test areas vary in soil composition, soil heterogeneity and precipitation regime. Accordingly, we consider the methodology of the model applicable in similar steep-sloped environments, which opens interesting perspectives for practitioners to plan future vegetation-based landslide management measures.

Author contribution

F.Z. is the main writer. B.S. contributed to the manuscript and embedding this research within previous research. C.P. contributed funding for the study and assisted with the manuscript. M.S. contributed to the manuscript and the concepts of the model.

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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